

Quanti Farm

**POLICY MONITORING
TOOL**

quantifarm.eu

FACTSHEET #4

[in](#) [f](#) [X](#) [@](#) [▶](#)

Funded by
the European Union

WHAT IS IT?

The **Policy Monitoring Tool** is an interactive component of the **QuantiFarm Toolkit** that supports the **monitoring and assessment of agricultural performance at the regional level**. It provides a **visual policy monitoring dashboard** that enables users to generate **analytical reports, summary tables, and graphical charts** based on user-defined queries.

The tool integrates **anonymised and aggregated farm-level data** from selected QuantiFarm Test Cases with **Earth Observation products, European GIS datasets, and official statistics**. By rendering data at the level of **Local Administrative Units (LAUs / Communes)**, it enables **qualitative and quantitative comparisons of regional agricultural performance and digitalisation impacts**.

KEY OBJECTIVES

To **support evidence-based policy monitoring and evaluation** in agriculture

To **analyse regional agricultural performance** using harmonised indicators

To **compare parcels using Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions (DATSs) with non-DATSs parcels**

To **assess the environmental, economic, and social impacts** of agricultural practices at the regional scale

To **provide benchmarking against regional thresholds and reference values**

To **strengthen transparency and comparability** of digitalisation impacts across regions

MAIN FEATURES

Interactive policy monitoring dashboard

Visualises regional data through maps, charts, and summary tables.

Multi-source data integration

Combines QuantiFarm Test Case data with Earth Observation products, European GIS datasets, and policy-relevant statistics (e.g., Eurostat, FADN).

Structured indicator framework

Provides access to 50 aggregated indicators organised into 13 thematic categories (e.g., fertilisers, water, energy, productivity, social indicators).

DATS vs. non- DATS comparison

Enables direct comparison of regional performance between parcels using DATSs and those using conventional practices.

Regional benchmarking

Contextualises results against established benchmarks and thresholds to assess regional 'standing.'

Customisation and export

Allows users to customise graphs and export data and visualisations in reusable formats (CSV, PNG, PDF, SVG).

Together, these features support robust, transparent, and scalable policy analysis on the impacts of digital agriculture.

MAIN FEATURES

WHO IS IT FOR?

Researchers and analysts

working on agricultural performance and sustainability

Advisors and other stakeholders

interested in regional evidence on digital agriculture impacts

Managing authorities

supporting agricultural programmes

Policymakers and public authorities

at the local, regional, and national levels

It supports users seeking **aggregated, comparable, and evidence-based insights** to inform policy design, monitoring, and evaluation.

Policy Monitoring Tool Access

The QuantiFarm Policy Monitoring Tool is available online through the project's official platform and continuously updated based on user feedback and new test results.

Contact

Funded by
the European Union

[quantifarm.eu](https://www.quantifarm.eu)
info@quantifarm.eu

